

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF LAMINATED PLATE WITH DISCRETE PLY ANGLES BASED ON GSFP METHOD

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1 Introduction

In engineering practice, there are always some limitations in fabrication of a laminated plate, such as the minimum thickness and material property of a ply, specific fiber orientation angle (for example, 0°, ±45°, 90°). For manufacturability, the thickness of each ply is usually the same, so the optimization problem of laminated plate can be described as an optimization problem with discrete variables, in which the ply angles are only selected from the specific discrete fiber orientation angles.

In this paper, continuous method for optimization with discrete variables is used [1-3]. There are two keys in continuous method. The first is to realize the continuous description of discrete variables, in which parameterization method should be studied. The second is how to transform the optimal design based on the continuous variables into design of reasonable discrete nature, namely, rounding off technique. According to most direct continuous method, continuation is realized by directly relaxing the limitation on discrete values and extending to a domain including all the discrete values of the original physical quantity, and reference of discrete nature is realized through rounding-off method. However, the continuous method has great influence on optimization results and rounding-off. For example, discrete variable $A_i \in \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ is transformed into $A_i \in [A_1, A_n]$ according to continuous method. If some design values are given to continuous variables after optimization, namely, $A_i^* \in [A_k, A_{k+1}]$, certain rule of rounding-off process will result in A_k or A_{k+1} (no other value). In this way, the possibility of better discrete values is restricted manually. As a result, study on appropriate parameterization method is important to realize continuation of the problem.

The method of Generalized Shape Function based Parameterization (GSFP) is proposed to solve the optimization problem with discrete variables, and the GSFP method can be seen as a common method for solving optimization problem of discrete material. So the optimization model of variable stiffness

laminated plate with discrete orientation angle based on GSFP method is proposed. It is found that sequence of admissible list and methods of punishment have important influence on result of optimization design. Ordering rule for admissible list with engineering orientation angles and quadratic penalty approach are given.

2 Problem Description

Finite element method was used to obtain the structural response. Variable stiffness design of lamina plate with discrete laying angle can be described as: To design a structure with maximum stiffness under a given loadings, the compliance is adopted as the objective function. The compliance C is expressed as: Given the material properties and thickness of single layer, the fiber angle can be selected from the candidate direction.

To design a structure with maximum stiffness under a given loadings, the compliance is adopted as the objective function. The compliance C is expressed as:

$$C = \int_{\Omega} f_i u_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} t_i u_i ds = F^T U \quad (1)$$

Where, consider a general body Ω subjected to applied body force f_i , and surface traction t_i on the surface Γ , U and F are total general nodal vectors of displacement and loading respectively. Obviously C is also the work done by the external force. The optimization model can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{find: } \mathbf{x} &= [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n] \\ \text{min: } C(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_i^{Nele} \mathbf{u}_i^T \mathbf{B}_i^T \left(\sum_{l=1}^{Nply} \mathbf{E}_{li} \right) \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}_i \quad (2) \\ \text{s.t. } \theta_i &\in \bar{\theta} = \{\bar{\theta}_1, \bar{\theta}_2, \dots, \bar{\theta}_{Nmat}\} \quad i=1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

Where X is the vector of design variables, $Nele$ is the total number of element in the design domain of laminate; $Nply$ is the number of layer; n is the number of design variable, and it can be express as: $n=Nele \times Nply$; $Nmat$ is the number of candidate directions in the candidate set; \mathbf{u}_i is the nodal

displacement vectors; B_i is the element strain matrix; E_{li} is the matrix of material properties for l th layer.

3 GSPF - General Shape Function Parameterization

3.1 Parameterization of discrete variables

In order to parameterize the discrete variables conveniently, two lists, named as “available list” and “admissible list”, are defined firstly. The “available list” means candidate materials set, being a known list of the materials, and the “admissible list” is a new list, a permutation of the elements of the available list based on a certain rule which is called as a sequential ordering rule in this paper and given in follow session. The value of design variables will be selected from “admissible list”.

The available list is recorded as $S_{List}=\{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{Nmat}\}$, $S_1 \leq S_2 \leq \dots \leq S_{Nmat}$. $Nmat$ is the length or the total element number of the available list, and restricted to $Nmat=2^N$. N is an integer which will be used, in following sessions, as the number of design variables describing the cross section of a structure component. S_{min} is assumed to be the minimum value of S_{List} . When $2^{N-l} < Nmat < 2^N$, $(2^N - Nmat)$ elements with cross-section area S_{min} are supplemented in S_{List} . The admissible list is determined as $A=\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{Nmat}\}$, which is a permutation of the elements in the list S_{List} according to some certain rules. Introduce parameter χ_m to represent the serial number of the element in available list S_{list} corresponding to the m -th element A_m of admissible list A , then the admissible list A can be determined by available list S_{List} ($A_m \in S_{List}$, $m = 1, \dots, Nmat$) and the corresponding sequence number χ_m . That is:

$$A = \left\{ (A_1, \dots, A_{Nmat}) \mid A_m = S_{\chi_m}, m = 1, 2, \dots, Nmat \right\} \quad (1)$$

Sequence order m is recorded as binary number as follows:

$$m = \sum_{i=1}^N a_{mi} 2^{(i-1)} + 1 \quad (2)$$

In equation (5), a_{mi} is the i -th bit in the binary of integer decimal m , equal to 0 or 1. N is the number of bit in the binary, which is determined by amount of elements in admissible list A .

Introduce indicating number ξ_{mi} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$), where the ξ_{mi} takes value 1 or -1.

$$\xi_{mi} = 2a_{mi} - 1 \text{ or } a_{mi} = (\xi_{mi} + 1)/2 \quad (3)$$

It can be known that ξ_{mi} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) is corresponding to elements in admissible list by substituting above equation in Equation (5). Therefore, ξ_{mi} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) can be regarded as descriptive parameters of elements in admissible list. As value of ξ_{mi} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) is 1 or -1, ξ_{mi} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) can be regarded as vertex coordinate of a hypercube in a N -dimensional space. The cube and vertex coordinate of $N=3$ are shown in Fig.1. The material properties can be indicated by coordinate R_i ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) in N -dimension space. Value of coordinate is only -1 or 1, to guarantee the vertexes of hypercube to be selected. The material property of design point can be expressed as the weighted sum of all candidate materials in the admissible list, that is

$$A = \sum_{m=1}^{Nmat} w_m (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N) A_m \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1 Coordinates of the unite hypercube ($N=3$)

A_m refers to the property of candidate material m in the admissible list; w_m refers to weight coefficient, with the definition:

$$w_m (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N) = \begin{cases} 1 & R_i = \xi_{mi}, i = 1, \dots, N \\ 0 & R_i \neq \xi_{mi} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Seen from the above equation, the material property varies with value of R_i ($i=1,2,\dots,N$). That is to say, R_i ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) can be regarded as descriptive parameter for material properties. The parameter is regarded as design variables, so the optimization of discrete

variable can be changed into the following formulation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{find : } \mathbf{x} = [R_{ij}^l] \\
 & \text{min : } C(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_i^{Nele} \mathbf{u}_i^T \mathbf{B}_i^T \left(\sum_{l=1}^{Nply} \mathbf{E}_{li} \right) \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}_i \quad (6) \\
 & \text{s.t. } R_{ij}^l \in \{-1, 1\}; \quad i = 1, \dots, Nele; \\
 & \quad \quad j = 1, \dots, Nevr; \quad l = 1, \dots, Nply;
 \end{aligned}$$

Tab. 1 Serial number m in the admissible list \mathbf{A} corresponding to the sequence number χ_m in the available list \mathbf{S}_{List}

$M($	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8																
N																								
$=3$																								
$)$																								
χ_m	2	3	1	8	6	7	5	4																
$M($	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1						
N										0	1	2	3	4	5	6								
$=4$																								
$)$																								
χ_m	4	5	6	7	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	8							
																		6	2	3	4	5	1	0

3.2 Formation of admissible list and sequential ordering rule

As defined in Section 3.1, the admissible list is a permutation of the elements in the beforehand available list. The selection of permutation may have great influence on the convergence. It's necessary to give a rational rule to determine the correspondence between m (the sequential number of element in admissible list) and χ_m (the sequential number of the corresponding element in available list) to make $A_m = S_{\chi_m}$.

Assume that the available list \mathbf{S}_{List} is the element list sorted from small to large: $S_1 \leq S_2 \leq \dots \leq S_{Nmat}$. Element in the available list \mathbf{S}_{List} are put into admissible list \mathbf{A} in accordance with certain sequence. Considering the assumption that the sequential numbers of elements in admissible list A_m are corresponding vertexes of a hypercube in space consisted of indicating number S_{χ_m} . The sequence rule of admissible list \mathbf{A} is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & A_{\frac{Nmat}{2}} = S_{Nmat}; \quad A_{Nmat} = S_{\frac{Nmat}{2}}; \\
 & \text{if } 1 \leq m \leq \frac{Nmat}{4}: \\
 & \quad A_m = S_{\frac{Nmat}{4}+m-1}; \quad A_{m+\frac{Nmat}{2}} = S_{\frac{3Nmat}{4}+m-1}; \quad (7) \\
 & \text{if } \frac{Nmat}{4}+1 \leq m \leq \frac{Nmat}{2}-1: \\
 & \quad A_m = S_{\frac{Nmat}{2}-m}; \quad A_{m+\frac{Nmat}{2}} = S_{Nmat-m};
 \end{aligned}$$

When the number of elements in admissible list \mathbf{A} is 8 ($N=3$) and 16 ($N=4$), the sequence number χ_m of available list \mathbf{S}_{List} corresponding to sequence number m in admissible list \mathbf{A} is shown in Table 1.

3.3 Continuation of discrete optimization problem

Continuation of optimization problem expressed by (9) is to loosen the limitation that design variables can only be 1 or -1. Firstly, feasible domain of design variables is extended from the discrete values to the domain $[-1, 1]$, a continuous domain which covered the discrete ones. Then, penalty technique is applied, so final result of design variables tends to be -1 or 1. The key of the question is to establish the material property when design variable are intermediate value (neither -1, nor 1). Inspired by the SFP method, a function (named as generalized shape function) just like in form to the shape function is interpolated as the weight factors in equation (7) in finite element method. This generalized shape function is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_m(R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N) &= \frac{1}{2^N} \prod_{k=1}^N (1 + \xi_{mk} R_k), \quad (8) \\
 m &= 1, \dots, Nmat
 \end{aligned}$$

In order to make the design variables converge to -1 or 1 as close as possible in continuous optimization model, we can therefore penalize weight in (10) with an exponent p in order to force the selection of only one material at the solution, thus limiting the occurrence of any blending of materials in a given physical ply at the optimum. The resulting GSFP scheme (SF with penalization) is written like this:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_m^{GSFP}(R_1, R_2, \dots, R_N) &= \left[\frac{1}{2^N} \prod_{k=1}^N (1 + \xi_{mk} R_k) \right]^p, \quad (9) \\
 m &= 1, \dots, Nmat
 \end{aligned}$$

After discrete variables are continued, optimization model (9) can be described as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{find : } \mathbf{x} &= [R_{ij}^l] \\ \text{min : } C(\mathbf{x}) &= \sum_i^{Nele} \mathbf{u}_i^T \mathbf{B}_i^T \left(\sum_{l=1}^{Nply} \mathbf{E}_{li} \right) \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{u}_i \quad (10) \\ \text{s.t. } -1 &\leq R_{ij}^l \leq 1; \quad i = 1, \dots, Nele; \\ & \quad j = 1, \dots, Nev; \quad l = 1, \dots, Nply; \end{aligned}$$

The p is assigned 2.0 in the optimization process.

4 Examples and discussion

In order to evaluate the convergence of the method, the ratio, CR, of the number, Nmid, of the design variables taken value within (-1, 1) to the total number, Nvar, of design variables is introduced to describe the convergence efficiency:

$$CR = \frac{Nmid}{Nvar} \quad (11)$$

Smaller CR indicates better convergence. One example was proposed and solved by Lund and Stegmann (2005) using the original DMO approach, and it is used to test the proposed method in this paper.

Example 1

A single-layer clamped plate subjected to uniform pressure is solved for minimum compliance. A sketch of the problem is shown in Fig.2. The plate has dimension $1.0m \times 1.0m \times 0.05m$ and is discretized by a 20×20 mesh of isoparametric 9-node degenerated elements. The material is orthotropic with $E_x=54GPa$, $E_y=E_z=18GPa$, $\nu=0.25$, $G_{xy}=G_{yz}=G_{xz}=9GPa$. Two groups of candidate directions are discussed. One is 8 candidate directions, $\{0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, 90^\circ\}$; and the other is 16 candidate directions, $\{0^\circ, \pm 15^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 35^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 55^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, \pm 75^\circ, 90^\circ\}$. In order to discuss the influence of the sequence order of the element in admissible list A, 2 different admissible lists with different sequences are given for every group. They can be expressed as following:

set81= $\{0^\circ, 90^\circ, -30^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ, -45^\circ, 45^\circ, -60^\circ\}$;
 set82= $\{-45^\circ, -30^\circ, -60^\circ, 90^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 30^\circ, 0^\circ\}$;
 set161= $\{-75^\circ, -60^\circ, -55^\circ, -45^\circ, -35^\circ, -30^\circ, -15^\circ, 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 35^\circ, 45^\circ, 55^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 90^\circ\}$;
 set162= $\{-45^\circ, -35^\circ, -30^\circ, -15^\circ, -55^\circ, -60^\circ, -75^\circ, 90^\circ, 45^\circ, 55^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 35^\circ, 30^\circ, 15^\circ, 0^\circ\}$;
 where set82 and set162 refer to corresponding sequence of elements of admissible list in available

list formed by the rule in the paper, Equation [13]; set81 and set161 refer to any random sequence.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of mechanical model of lamina

Table 1: Optimal results of optimization

Name	Penal factor	Iteration	CR	objective
set81	$p=2.0$	3	0	2.190
set82	$p=2.0$	3	0	1.670
set161	$p=2.0$	4	0	1.778
set162	$p=2.0$	4	0	1.690

Fig. 3 Fiber angle distribution in lamina. (a) the distribution for set81; (b) the distribution for set82

Fig. 4 Fiber angle distribution in lamina for $p=1.0$. (a) distribution for set81; (b) distribution for set82

Example 2

A symmetry laminated plate with 8 equal layers having a length $a=b=0.1m$, thickness $h=0.004m$ is analyzed with fully clamped and subjected to

uniform transverse loading. The optimal results are given below (Fig. 5):

Fig. 5 Fiber angle distribution in layers

5 Conclusion

A generalized shape based parameterization (GSFP) method for variable stiffness laminated plate with discrete orientation angle is proposed. It is found that sequence of admissible list has important influence on result of optimization design. Ordering

rule for admissible list with engineering orientation angles is given.

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